

Use of Potassium Chromithiocyanate as a Developer in Paper Chromatography

M. P. Gupta and M. L. Anand*

Potassium chromithiocyanate forms coloured precipitates with a number of metallic salt solutions in neutral and acidic medium¹. The colours of the precipitates are milk-rose for silver, dirty-white for thallium, brownish red for mercury, light yellowish brown for lead and brick red for bismuth. In the present communication, potassium chromithiocyanate has been tried for detection of Ag, Pb, Hg, Bi & Tl in presence of each other and in admixture of some other metals by employing filter paper chromatography.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium chromithiocyanate was prepared and standardised by methods adopted by Boesler² and Bjerrum³. Standard solutions of silver nitrate, lead nitrate, mercuric chloride, bismuth nitrate, thalious sulphate, copper nitrate and cadmium sulphate were prepared using reagent grade chemicals (B.D.H.). The method adopted was the strip filter paper descending chromatographic technique, using an arrangement described by Gage, Douglass and Wender⁴. Whatman filter paper No. 1 was used throughout. For the separation of Ag, Pb, Hg, Bi and Tl, the solvent dioxane-antipyrine-HNO₃-H₂O has proved more suitable in comparison to others under the experimental conditions. Solvent dioxane-antipyrine-nitric acid-water was prepared by dissolving 1.0 gm. of antipyrine in a mixture of 100 ml of pure dioxane, 1 ml of conc. HNO₃ and 2.5 ml of water. The chromatograms were run under ordinary conditions in a room with temperature range 22° to 28° and the time allowed was 3 to 4 hr. for diffusion for dioxane-antipyrine-nitric acid-water mixture solvent. Majumdar and Chakrabarty⁵ have stressed the usefulness of R_L and R_T values over R_F values in ascertaining good separation. Hence R_L and R_T values have been measured instead of R_F values. In binary, ternary, quaternary and pentanary mixtures the final concentration of each metal ion was kept between 0.1 M to 0.01 M.

* Present address: Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

1. Gupta and Anand, Unpublished observation.
2. *Roseler Annalen*, 1867, 141, 185.
3. Bjerrum, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.* 1921, 118, 131.
4. Gage, Douglas and Wender *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1950, 27, 159
5. Majumdar and Chakrabarty, *Anal. chim. Acta.*, 1957, 17, 415.

In the case of Ag, Pb, Hg, Bi and Tl ions only fresh solution of potassium chromithiocyanate was tried as a developing agent. But when the mixtures of these metal ions with other metal ions were tried, a mixture of potassium chromithiocyanate and potassium ferrocyanide solutions and H₂S vapours have been also employed for visual detection. Photographs have been omitted for economy of space.

Binary Mixtures.—Binary mixtures of Ag-Pb, Ag-Hg, Ag-Bi, Ag-Tl, Pb-Hg, Pb-Bi, Pb-Tl, Hg-Bi, Hg-Tl and Bi-Tl have been employed where only potassium chromithiocyanate was used as developer. R_L & R_T values have been recorded in Table No. 1. Binary mixtures of Hg-Cu, Cd-Hg, Pb-Cu, Pb-Cd, Bi-Cu, Bi-Cd, Tl-Cd, Ag-Cu and Ag-Cd have been effected where potassium chromithiocyanate, potassium ferrocyanide or H₂S vapour have been used as developers. R_L & R_T values have been recorded in Table No. 5.

Ternary Mixtures.—Ternary mixtures of Ag-Pb-Hg, Ag-Hg-Bi, Ag-Bi-Tl, Ag-Tl-Pb, Pb-Hg-Bi, Pb-Bi-Ag, Hg-Bi-Tl and Hg-Tl-Pb have been separated and developed as in case of binary mixtures. R_L & R_T values have been recorded in Table No. 2. R_L & R_T values of ions present in ternary mixtures of Hg-Bi-Cu, Hg-Cu-Cd, Hg-Pb-Cd, Pb-Bi-Cu, Pb-Cu-Cd, Bi-Cu-Cd, Pb-Bi-Cd, Ag-Cu-Cd have been recorded in Table No. 6.

Quaternary Mixtures.—Quaternary mixtures of Ag-Pb-Hg-Bi, Pb-Hg-Bi-Tl, Hg-Bi-Tl-Ag, Bi-Tl-Ag-Pb and Tl-Ag-Pb-Hg have been separated and developed. R_L & R_T values have been recorded in Table No. 3. Quaternary mixtures of Hg-Pb-Bi-Cu, Hg-Bi-Cu-Cd, Pb-Bi-Cu-Cd, Hg-Pb-Bi-Cd and Hg-Pb-Cu-Cd have been separated and developed with a mixture of potassium chromithiocyanate, potassium ferrocyanide and H₂S vapours. R_L & R_T values have been recorded in Table No. 7.

TABLE 1

Strip No.	Ag ⁺		Pb ²⁺		Hg ²⁺		Bi ³⁺		Tl ⁺	
	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T
1.	0.27	0.16	0.50	0.95						
2.	0.19	0.00			0.65	0.15				
3.	0.23	0.13					0.86	0.71		
4.	0.21	0.13							0.16	0.07
5.			0.99	0.02	0.79	0.14				
6.			0.46	0.33			0.87	0.73		
7.			0.42	0.34					0.15	0.03
8.					0.62	0.32	0.84	0.65		
9.					0.65	0.12			0.12	0.01
10.							0.90	0.65	0.17	0.04

TABLE 2

1.	0.21	0.08	0.43	0.29	0.52	0.21				
2.	0.19	0.08			0.65	0.50	0.86	0.60		
3.	0.18	0.08					0.96	0.73	0.14	0.04
4.	0.20	0.10	0.41	0.27					0.16	0.03
5.			0.56	0.25	0.63	0.50	0.83	0.62		
6.	0.19	0.11	0.40	0.31			0.92	0.84		
7.					0.62	0.47	0.90	0.56	0.14	0.03
8.			0.35	0.29	0.73	0.53			0.13	0.02

TABLE 3

Strip No.	Ag ⁺		Pb ²⁺		Hg ²⁺		Bi ³⁺		Tl ⁺	
	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T
1.	0.26	0.14	0.14	0.31	0.67	0.60	0.88	0.78	0.21	0.03
2.			0.35	0.21	Streaked		0.88	0.64	0.18	0.04
3.	0.19	0.09			Streaked		0.90	0.61	0.15	0.04
4.	0.18	0.08	0.34	0.27			0.89	0.75	0.15	0.04
5.	0.21	0.10	0.40	0.30	0.81	0.57				

TABLE 4

1.	0.10	0.01	Blank	0.68	0.42	0.87	0.64	0.04	0.00
----	------	------	-------	------	------	------	------	------	------

TABLE 5

Strip No.	Ag ⁺		Pb ²⁺		Hg ²⁺		Bi ³⁺		Cu ²⁺		Cd ²⁺		Tl ⁺	
	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T	R _L	R _T
1.					0.68	0.40			0.46	0.07				
2.					0.87	0.58					0.53	0.00		
3.			0.51	—					0.46	0.21				
4.			Blank								0.36	0.17		
5.							0.88	0.74	0.50	0.16				
6.							0.83	0.71			0.37	0.20		
7.											0.28	0.10	0.11	0.03
8.	0.18	0.02							0.49	0.13				
9.	0.18	0.01									0.30			

TABLE 6

1.					0.72	0.38	0.82	0.73	0.43	0.05				
2.					0.82	0.48			0.44	0.14			obscure	
3.			0.62	0.31	0.86	0.60					0.43	0.17		
4.			Blank				0.87	0.80	0.46	0.25				
5.			0.50	—					0.44	0.21			obscure	
6.							0.88	0.57	0.48	0.11	0.45	0.30		
7.			0.62	—			0.88	0.63			0.44	0.13		
8.	0.18	0.00							0.53	0.17	0.52	0.32		

TABLE 7

1.			obscure		0.91	0.49	0.91	0.79	0.34	0.18				
2.					—	0.55	0.86	0.83	0.40	0.11			obscure	
3.					blank		0.85	0.70	0.45	0.22			obscure	
4.					—	0.51	0.88	0.78	0.38	0.18	0.44		—	
5.			Blank		0.77	0.45			0.42	0.10			obscure	

TABLE 8

1.			—	0.47	0.76	0.50	0.89	0.86	0.38	0.21	—		0.16
----	--	--	---	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	---	--	------

Pentanary Mixtures.—A solution containing Ag-Pb-Hg, Bi & Tl was subjected to separation. The detection of Tl, Ag and Bi was very distinct. Hg streaked out whereas Pb spot was absent due to $PbSO_4$ present in suspension in pentanary solution. R_L & R_T values have been recorded in Table No.4. In the development of pentanary mixture Hg-Pb-Bi-Cu-Cd, Cu-Cd overlapped with each other. Hg streaked out, Pb not very distinct whereas Bi was distinct and aloof. R_L & R_T values have been recorded in Table No. 8.

After going through the R_L & R_T values it has been concluded that good separation may be obtained suggesting a very nice use in detection of these metals with only one reagent by paper chromatography.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
MEERUT COLLEGE,
MEERUT.

Received April 19, 1966